

Supplementary Figure 2. List of SEED articles

Full-text or Abstract	Authors	Title	Publication	Year	PMID	Database Source	Found by Scopus Citation Searching?	Found by Google Scholar Citation Searching?	Found by PubMed Search?
Abstract	Ågerstrand, Marlene; Bretholz, Magnus; Rudén, Christina;	Reporting and Evaluating Ecotoxicity Data for Environmental Risk Assessment: How Can Current Practices Be Improved?	Comprehensive Analytical Chemistry	2013	N/A	Scopus	Yes		No - book series not indexed by PubMed
Full-text	Berger, E; Coja, T; Dellantonio, A; Hrdina-Zödl, B; Hutzenlaub, N; Jölli, D; Möller, M; Prohaska, C;	Case studies for the application of the Guidance of EFSA on Submission of scientific peer-reviewed open literature for the approval of pesticide active substances under Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009, using substances for which dossiers are submitted under Regulation (EU) No 1141/2010	EFSA Supporting Publications	2013	N/A	N/A - can be searched at https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/	No	Yes	No - journal not indexed by PubMed
Full-text	Burns, Emily E; Davies, Iain A;	Coral ecotoxicological data evaluation for the environmental safety assessment of ultraviolet filters	Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry	2021	34758162	PubMed	Yes		No
Full-text	Card, Jeffrey W; Magnuson, Bernadene A;	A method to assess the quality of studies that examine the toxicity of engineered nanomaterials	International Journal of Toxicology	2010	20634541	PubMed	Yes		No
Full-text	European Food Safety Authority;	Submission of scientific peer-reviewed open literature for the approval of pesticide active substances under Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009	EFSA Journal	2011	N/A	Scopus	Yes		No - journal not indexed by PubMed
Full-text	Fewtrell, Loma; Majuru, Batsira; Hunter, Paul R.	A re-assessment of the safety of silver in household water treatment: rapid systematic review of mammalian in vivo genotoxicity studies	Environmental Health	2017	28633660	PubMed	Yes		Yes
Full-text	Gimenes, Izabela; Pinto, Andréa V; Braga da Silva Sardinha, Mariana; Maranhão-Vásquez, Guido A.; Gonzalez, Marcelo S.; Presgrave, Octávio A.; Maia, Lucianne C.; Alves, Gutemberg G.	Cold Storage Media versus Optisol-GS in the Preservation of Corneal Quality for Keratoplasty: A Systematic Review	Applied Sciences	2022	N/A	Scopus	Yes		No - journal not indexed by PubMed
Full-text	Gross, Melanie; Green, Richard M; Weltje, Lennart; Wheeler, James R;	Weight of evidence approaches for the identification of endocrine disrupting properties of chemicals: Review and recommendations for EU regulatory application	Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology	2017	28986177	PubMed	Yes		No
Full-text	Haighton, Lois; Roberts, Ashley; Walters, Brandon; Lynch, Barry;	Systematic review and evaluation of aspartame: carcinogenicity bioassays using quality criteria	Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology	2019	29339245	PubMed	Yes		No
Abstract	Isigonis, Panagiotis; Cliffroy, Philippe; Zabeo, Alex; Semenzin, Elena; Critto, Andrea; Giove, Silvio; Marcomini, Antonio;	A Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis based methodology for quantitatively scoring the reliability and relevance of ecotoxicological data	Science of the Total Environment	2015	26298253	PubMed	Yes		No
Abstract	Jung, Jae-Woong; Kang, Jae-Soon; Choi, Jinsoo; Park, June-Woo;	Chronic toxicity of endocrine disrupting chemicals used in plastic products in Korean resident species: Implications for aquatic ecological risk assessment	Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety	2020	32061985	PubMed	Yes		No
Full-text	Kandhare, Amit D; Thakurdesai, Prasad A; Wangkar, Prahad; Bodhankar, Subhash L;	A systematic literature review of fenugreek seed toxicity by using ToxRTool: evidence from preclinical and clinical studies	Heliyon	2019	31049444	PubMed	Yes		Yes
Full-text	Kirkland, David; Aardema, Marilyn E; Battensby, Rüdiger V; Bevers, Carol; Burnett, Karin; Burlaff, Ame; Cich, Andreas; Donner, E Maria; Fowler, Paul; Johnston, Helinor J.;	A weight of evidence review of the genotoxicity of titanium dioxide (TiO ₂)	Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology	2022	36228836	PubMed	Yes		No
Abstract	Koch, Michael S.; DeSesso, John M.; Williams, Amy Lavin; Michalek, Suzanne; Hammond, Bruce	Adaptation of the ToxRTool to Assess the Reliability of Toxicology Studies Conducted with Genetically Modified Crops and Implications for Future Safety Testing	Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition	2016	25208336	PubMed	Yes		Yes
Full-text	Kodimasis, Albert A; Nor, Nur Huzimah Mohamed; Hermen, Enya; Kooi, Merel; Mintenlig, Svenja M; De France, Jennifer;	Microplastics in freshwaters and drinking water: Critical review and assessment of data quality	Water research	2019	30861380	PubMed	Yes		No
Full-text	Kose, Ozge; Manteca, Paride; Costa, Anna; Carlière, Marie;	Putative adverse outcome pathways for silver nanoparticle toxicity on mammalian male reproductive system: A literature review	Particle and Fibre Toxicology	2023	36604752	PubMed	Yes		Yes
Full-text	Li, Yan; Luo, Guijie; Guo, Ping;	The inhibitory effect of dihydroartemisinin on non-small cells lung cancer	Pharmacological Research-Modern Chinese Medicine	2021	N/A	Scopus	Yes		No - journal not indexed by PubMed
Full-text	Magnuson, Bernadene A; Jonatis, Tomas S; Card, Jeffrey W;	A brief review of the occurrence, use, and safety of food-related nanomaterials	Journal of food science	2011	22417518	PubMed	Yes		No
Abstract	Mendez, Fabian; Ochoa-Fetancourth, Jenny; Abrahams, Nathalie;	Effects of Glyphosate Exposure on Reproductive Health: A Systematic Review of Human, Animal and In-Vitro Studies	Exposure and Health	2022	N/A	Scopus	Yes		No - journal not fully indexed by PubMed
Full-text	Moermond, Caroline TA; Kase, Robert; Kofstad, Muris; Ågerstrand, Marlene	CRED: Criteria for reporting and evaluating ecotoxicity data	Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry	2016	26399705	PubMed	Yes		No
Full-text	Moser, Virginia C; Momi-Schaffer, Keith; Richardson, Jason R; Li, Abby A	Glyphosate and neurological outcomes: A systematic literature review of animal studies	Journal of Toxicology and Environmental Health, Part B	2022	35676826	PubMed	Yes		Yes
Full-text	Neal, BH; Bus, J; Marty, MS; Coady, K; Williams, A; Staveley, J; Lamb, JC;	Weight-of-evidence evaluation of 2, 4-D potential for interactions with the estrogen, androgen and thyroid pathways and steroidogenesis	Critical Reviews in Toxicology	2017	28303741	PubMed	Yes		No
Full-text	Nhu, Nguyen Thanh; Li, Qing; Liu, Yijie; Xu, Jian; Xiao, Shu-Yun; Lee, Shin-Da	Effects of Mdivi-1 on Neural Mitochondrial Dysfunction and Mitochondria-Mediated Apoptosis in Ischemia-Reperfusion Injury After Stroke: A Systematic Review of Preclinical Studies	Frontiers in Molecular Neuroscience	2021	35002619	PubMed	Yes		Yes
Abstract	Piñeda-Zayas, Alejandro; Menéndez López-Mateos, Luisa; Palma-Fernández, Juan Carlos; Iglesias-Linares, Alejandro	Assessment of metal ion accumulation in oral mucosa cells of patients with fixed orthodontic treatment and cellular DNA damage: a systematic review	Critical Reviews in Toxicology	2021	34738508	PubMed	Yes		Yes
Full-text	Sanchez, Priscila Laviola; Queaquinto, Luths Raquel de Oliveira; Cruz, Rebecca; Schuck, Desiree Cigaran; Lorenzini, Marcio; Granjeiro, José Mauro; Ribeiro, Ana Rosa Lopes;	Toxicity evaluation of TiO ₂ nanoparticles on the 3D skin model: A systematic review	Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology	2020	32587852	PubMed	Yes		Yes
Abstract	Warne, Michael St J; King, Olivia; Smith, Rachael A;	Ecotoxicity thresholds for ametryn, diuron, hexazinone and simazine in fresh and marine waters	Environmental Science and Pollution Research	2018	2933279	PubMed	Yes		No
Full-text	Willhite, Calvin C; Kayakina, Nataliya A; Yokel, Robert A; Venugodhath, Nagarajkumar; Wisniewski, Thomas M; Arnold, Ian MF; Momoli, Franco; Krewski, Daniel;	Systematic review of potential health risks posed by pharmaceutical, occupational and consumer exposures to metallic and nanoscale aluminum, aluminum oxides, aluminum hydroxide and its soluble salts	Critical reviews in toxicology	2014	25233067	PubMed	Yes		No
Full-text	Williams, Amy Lavin; Bates, Christopher A; Pace, Nelson D; Leonhard, Megan J; Chang, Ellen T; DeSesso, John M;	Impact of chloroform exposures on reproductive and developmental outcomes: A systematic review of the scientific literature	Birth Defects Research	2018	30350414	PubMed	Yes		No

Supplementary Figure 2. List of SEED articles. This sample provides the details for each of the 28 articles used to confirm the search strategy in Supplementary Table 2, finalize the eligibility criteria in Table 3, and develop the key characteristics in Table 2.